

until panicle initiation.

Varieties VHC 1253, Lengkwang, Hawang Haedo, VL 206, L 105-8, VLK39, and Himdhan had poor early seedling growth but recovered rapidly when the temperature rose above 25°C. They reached a par in vigor with the earliest varieties in both years.

A similar set of varieties was evaluated

under controlled conditions. Twenty-five seeds of each were placed in petri dishes containing a mixture of sand, soil, and water. The same set of 10 varieties that performed well in the first experiment had more than 80% germination at 11 °C.

The third experiment had 16 varieties planted in pots. At booting stage, one set of pots was transferred to 2,400 m alti-

tude where night temperatures were 10° to 5 °C. Another set was maintained at 1,600 m altitude where night temperatures were 18° to 12 °C. Only L 62G, Khonorullo, L 62-2A, UPRH299, and L 12-1A had good spikelet fertility and leaf color at 2,400 m altitude. Olbyed, Gangweondo, JC99, and Nancee had normal leaf color. □

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Effect of urea foliar spraying on rice tungro virus (RTV) infection

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In Mar-May 1984 there was a severe outbreak of RTV on several rice varieties in North Arcot District, Tamil Nadu. We tested a 1% foliar spraying of urea for RTV control on susceptible IET1722 at different sites. Disease incidence was measured at first spraying (20 d after transplanting [DT] and 20 d before harvest, using the Standard evaluation system for rice.

At first spraying 5-10% RTV infection

Effect of foliar application of urea on RTV infection, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Disease incidence (%)		Mean yield (t/ha)
	20 d after transplanting	20 d before harvest	
1% urea sprayed at 20, 30, 40, and 50 d + phosphamidon (85% EC) at 20 and 35 d after transplanting	7 - 8	7 - 10	4.2
Phosphamidon (85% EC) sprayed at 20 and 35 d after transplanting	6 - 7	38 - 41	2.4
No treatment control	5 - 9	60 - 72	1.2

was recorded. Foliar application of 1% urea at 20, 30, 40, and 50 DT + phosphamidon (85% EC) 320 ml/ha at 20 and 35 DT effectively controlled RTV up to

10% infection. In phosphamidon-treated and control fields, disease spread was 41 and 72% with a corresponding yield reduction (see table). □

New rice grassy stunt virus (GSV) strain in Thailand

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Rice plants with symptoms of an unknown disease and other virus diseases were collected at several sites in Thailand and tested for virus presence by immune electron microscopy (IEM) and the dipping method. For IEM, grids were treated with an antiserum to rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) or rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) at 1 : 1000 dilution. After incubation with sap of plant samples, grids were floated on anti-

Table 1. Detection by IEM technique and dipping method of viruses from rice plants with different virus symptoms. ^a

Variety	Symptoms (visual assessment)	Virus particles detected by dipping	Reaction of extracts in IEM to antiserum against	
			RTSV	RTBV
Kaimukdum pl. no. 1	RSV	RSV	-	-
Kaimukdum pl. no. 2	RSV	RSV	-	-
Kaimukdum pl. no. 3	RTV	RTSV	+	-
Kaimukdum pl. no. 4	RTV	RTBV	-	+
Kaimukdum pl. no. 5	RTV	RTSV, RTBV	+	+
Kaimukdum pl. no. 6	RSV	RSV	-	-
Kaimukdum pl. no. 7	RSV, unknown	RSV	-	-
Kaimukdum pl. no. 8	unknown	-	-	-
Apple Thong pl. no. 1	unknown	-	-	-
Apple Thong pl. no. 2	unknown	-	-	-
Number 20 pl. no. 1	unknown	-	-	-
Number 20 pl. no. 2	unknown	-	-	-
Number 20 pl. no. 3	unknown	-	-	-

^a + and - indicate positive and negative reactions. RSV = rice ragged stunt, RTV = rice tungro virus.